

1 **Phc1/2 modulation during TE specification in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Phc1
9 and Phc2 as lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem
10 cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Chen, L., Tong, Q., Chen, X., Jiang, P., Yu, H., Zhao, Q., Sun, L., Liu, C., Gu, B., Zheng, Y. and
13 Fei, L., 2021. PHC1 maintains pluripotency by organizing genome-wide chromatin interactions of the
14 Nanog locus. *Nature Communications*, 12(1), p.2829.

15 2. Isono, K., Endo, T.A., Ku, M., Yamada, D., Suzuki, R., Sharif, J., Ishikura, T., Toyoda, T.,
16 Bernstein, B.E. and Koseki, H., 2013. SAM domain polymerization links subnuclear clustering of PRC1 to
17 gene silencing. *Developmental cell*, 26(6), pp.565-577.

18 3. Guan, S., Tang, J., Ma, X., Miao, R. and Cheng, B., 2024. CBX7C · PHC2 interaction facilitates
19 PRC1 assembly and modulates its phase separation properties. *Iscience*, 27(4).